

FORMATION OF THE MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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***Abstract.** This article is about management methods and techniques in educational institutions the opinions and comments of research scientists on the topic of improvement was studied in depth. In today's information technology era, it is innovative and electronic the use of programs is finding its place not only in the IT sector, but also in the education system. Implementation of a unified information space of pedagogical educational institutions of pedagogical education creates good conditions for the development of quality and information supply.*

***Keywords:** interactive communication, pedagogical software tools, communication service, pedagogical skills, creativity, innovative methods, modern information technologies, web technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

Fulfilling the tasks set by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of higher education largely depends on the personality of the teacher [1]. Teaching is an honorable but very difficult profession. Achieving the goal of education in the conditions of the transition to the market economy, organizing various activities of students, raising them to be educated, polite, faithful, hardworking, business-minded, well-rounded people entrusted with. The future of our people, the prospects of Uzbekistan in many ways to the teacher, his level, training, dedication, to the work of teaching and educating the young generation depends on the relationship. Master pedagogical theory to become a good teacher alone is not enough. Because in pedagogical theory it is about teaching and educating children general rules, principles, generalized methodical ideas are described, it is emphasized to take into account the age and individual characteristics of students [6]. University life and the practical pedagogical process are very diverse and complex. Pedagogical there are many situations that do not correspond to the theory. This is more than a teacher requires knowledge, thorough practical training and high pedagogical skills and creativity is enough. In order to become a true master of a profession, a person has a natural ability, a certain physical and there should be mental qualities, thorough preparation, some personal qualities. A person who chooses the profession of pedagogy must first be healthy, be able to pronounce words correctly and well, be calm and composed, and be able to maintain self-control in dealing with others. Also, it is necessary for the teacher to have personal qualities such as liking students, willingness to work with them, politeness, observation, ability to think broadly, organization, demanding towards himself and others [3].

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

With the development of technology, it is the only one to teach using technical tools the presence of a computer is enough. In addition, information transfer, International scientific-

practical conference on the topic of "Problems and perspectives of modern technology in teaching foreign languages" the quality of storage and imaging has increased significantly. To date computer literacy has become an important sign of culture, and in the future it will become a necessity for every person, no matter where he works. So computer work, computer training will undoubtedly become commonplace in the near future [2].

Modern information technology tools include: computer, scanner, video camera, LCD projector, interactive whiteboard, fax modem, telephone, e-mail, multimedia tools, Internet networks, mobile communication systems, data storage control systems, artificial intelligence systems can be included.

In the educational process, computers are mainly used in four ways:

- passive application - the computer is like a simple counter;
- reactive communication - the computer as an examiner;
- active communication - when guiding a computer student and taking an exam;
- interactive communication - the computer as artificial intelligence, that is, when communicating with the student is used.

Wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in education:

- informatization of science fields;
- intellectualization of educational activity;
- deepening of integration processes;
- by improving the infrastructure of the educational system and its management mechanisms will come.

Effective organization of pedagogical education processes based on modern information technologies achieve:

- pedagogues for the team creating distance learning courses and electronic literature, the association of computer programmers, relevant specialists;
- distribution of tasks among pedagogues;
- improvement of educational process organization and pedagogical activities requires monitoring of its effectiveness.

Implementation of modern information technologies in educational processes:

- the student acquires professional knowledge;
- deepen the field of science by modeling the studied phenomena and processes to be assimilated;
- independent activity of the student due to the diverse organization of educational activities expansion of the field;
- educational process based on the introduction of interactive communication opportunities to individualization and differentiation;
- the student's learning materials by using the capabilities of the artificial intelligence system mastering the mastering strategy;
- formation of information culture in him as a member of the information society;
- presentation of the studied processes and events by means of computer technologies,

It is a profession of great importance as it leads to increasing interest and activity in the fundamentals of science among students is enough.

The concept of pedagogical software tools

Pedagogical software tools are didactic tools designed for partial or complete automation of the learning process with the help of computer technologies. They are considered one of the promising forms of increasing the efficiency of the educational process and are used as a teaching tool of modern technologies. Pedagogical software tools include: a software product (set of programs) aimed at achieving specific didactic goals in a subject, technical and methodical support, additional auxiliary tools.

Pedagogical software tools can be divided into the following:

^ educational programs - based on the level of knowledge and interests of students, they guide the acquisition of new knowledge;

^ test programs - checking or evaluating acquired knowledge, skills and abilities used for its purposes;

^ trainers (trainers) - repetition of previously mastered educational material and serves to strengthen;

^ Virtual presence systems - the creator of a virtual learning environment with the participation of the teacher programs.

Use of practical and pedagogical software tools in pedagogical activity

In order to implement the technology of creating pedagogical software tools, there are a number of positive factors that confirm their superiority over traditional tools. These factors were divided into didactic, psychological, economic and physiological groups.

Didactic requirements for pedagogical software tools include: together with scientificity, understandable, strict and systematic description (pedagogy, psychology, the main principles of informatics, international scientific-practical of modern science conference on the topic of "Problems and perspectives of modern technology in teaching abroad languages", the possibility of building the content of educational activities, taking into account the fundamental principles providing), continuity and integrity (a logical consequence of previously learned knowledge and is a filler), consistency, problem, demonstrability, activation (teaching independence and the presence of the characteristic of activity), assimilation of learning results consistency, interactivity of communication, teaching, training, development and practice whole unit.

Methodological requirements include: taking into account the specific characteristics of a particular academic discipline, taking into account the uniqueness of a particular discipline, the interdependence, interrelationship, diversity, implementation of modern methods of information.

Psychological requirements include perception (verbal-logical, sensory-perceptive), thinking (conceptual-theoretical, demonstrative-practical), attention (persistence, transference), motivation (active forms of work, high degree of visibility, using timely feedback constant stimulation of high level motivation of students), taking into account memory, imagination, age and individual psychological characteristics (taking into account acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications, the content of academic subjects and the level of complexity of educational issues, the age of students matching capabilities and individual characteristics, protection from being affected by excessive emotional, nervous, mental loads when learning the learning material) enters.

Technical requirements for modern universal personal computers, peripherals, testing include transferable resources.

Client-server architecture, Internet browsers, network operation for network requirements systems, telecommunications, management tools (individual and collective training process works, external feedback).

Aesthetic requirements include: orderliness and expressiveness (elements, location, size, color), functional function of decoration and compliance with ergonomic requirements.

Specific requirements include: interactivity, goal orientation, independence and flexibility, audioization, visualization, access control, intellectual development, differentiation (classification), creativity, openness, feedback, functionality, reliability.

Ergonomic requirements include: friendliness, user adaptability, screen organization of forms.

Methodological requirements are the study designed for teaching on the basis of pedagogical software tools specific features of science, its laws, research methods, information processing considers the possibilities of introducing modern methods of giving.

Use of Internet resources in the educational process. Web sites in educational processes there are many benefits to using. Therefore, the creation and content of such sites Renovation plays an important role in the activity of a higher education institution. So it is Creating dedicated sites for educational institutions is in front of every educational institution is among the primary tasks. The creation of such sites is during the study of the Internet factors related to the system should be taken into account. Mention the following as such factors can:

- the breadth of Internet service opportunities worldwide;
- ease of use of website service;
- ease of distribution of web technologies;
- requirements for information on a real-time scale;
- information about institutions and private individuals themselves to the Internet seeking placement;
- collection of optional information on a global scale in the network database [8].

The importance of Internet technologies for sites created for an educational institution the breadth of possibilities and simplicity of Internet users is increasing every minute is leading to go. Of course, the majority of users are students, it is organized by students and staff engaged in scientific research. Based on this, say possible from Internet technologies in the educational process, in particular to educational institutions the use of dedicated websites significantly increases the quality and efficiency of education helps to bring it to the stage.

New information technology tools are improving and developing now of students studying at an educational institution under the conditions (activity in any field in general providers) can find the necessary information independently from the Internet system, they face it is important to be able to fully and correctly solve the problems related to the existing specialty is becoming one of the conditions [10].

Possibilities of using Internet sites in the educational process, its effectiveness it is very important to determine the types of Internet service and their nature is important. It is this identified information that is the organization of work on the Internet helps to distinguish forms and methods. Based on the classification you can get the way the internet works. In this case, the Internet server services are divided into two: informational and should be divided into types of communication services.

WWW (information complex) and GTR (program complex) are included in the information service.

The communication service can be divided into two types: direct (PC, chat) and indirect communication (e-mail, forum, teleconference).

All "sites created for an educational institution" on the Internet can be divided into several types:

- educational Internet resources;
- consulting Internet resources;
- informative Internet sources;
- evaluative Internet sources;
- Internet resources with presentations;

Below we will discuss each of them separately.

Examples of online learning resources include distance learning, virtual schools, labs, and web classrooms.

Examples of Internet sources of advice include various teleconferences, virtual pedagogical councils, virtual methodical, associational problem councils, virtual cafes, etc.

Informational Internet sources include electronic textbooks, reference books, electronic libraries, dictionaries, catalogs, and virtual museums.

Evaluative Internet sources include teletesting, remote contests, various quizzes, and olympiads.

About the educational directions of educational institutions to the presented Internet resources separate pages with detailed information can be cited [11].

Teachers to learners using sites created for educational institutions they make it possible for them to learn from a distance. Created for educational institutions the sites are particularly accessible to learners who find it difficult to attend teaching sites. Of this culture of working with information technologies, skills and they will have the qualifications in the course of the lesson from the sites created for educational institutions use creates great opportunities.

Teaching with the help of sites created for educational institutions, the educational process is traditional includes the main forms of organization. Lecture, seminar and practical training, laboratory practice, control system, scientific research and independent work of students including All these forms of educational process organization are in practice the activity of independent knowledge of listeners can be easily combined with various sources of information, course quick and systematic communication with the leading teacher and group of listeners gives the opportunity to do things [12].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Use of sites created for educational institutions in the educational process to teachers:

- experiences and methods collected from one or another educational subject using the Internet exchange with other colleagues;
- implement different teaching methods for different categories of students at the same time individualization of the educational process by increasing;
- as an exercise from control assignments on sites created for educational institutions as a result of the use of the acquired knowledge in the subject in students, skills and competences to bring to the level;

- allowing students to work individually due to the reduction of manual work and create an opportunity to demonstrate their abilities;
- opportunities such as effective organization of students' independent learning process creates. Students use sites created for educational institutions in teaching:
 - choose study situations according to their preferences;
 - study according to their preparation and psychophysical characteristics selection of methods and methods of expression;
 - to return to previously studied materials, to suspend the study process and to it to apply at any time;
 - monitoring the dynamics of various processes and the interaction of mechanisms;
 - management of studied objects and review of their corresponding results;
 - communication on the computer should be free of psychological obstacles (laughter). not to be, not to dare, not to be ashamed) to bring;
 - such as using computers patiently until training levels are sufficient will have opportunities.

The following advantages of sites created for educational institutions in the field of education

can be listed:

- improvement of mastering of subjects;
- increasing network literacy (communicating with computers and the Internet news);
- improved attitude to learning;
- improvement of independent education and research skills;
- increase the effectiveness of practical skills.

Sites created for an educational institution on the Internet Today, development is very fast and changing very fast. Almost every minute changes, updates and unexpected events in different parts of the planet events are happening. Every day we live under a strong flow of information. Information flow follows us at home, at work and on vacation. Normal activity free from the influence of human information can't walk Understanding life, studying it by collecting and absorbing information will pass. The level of knowledge of a person is also acquired by an individual within a certain period of time it is determined by the amount or the amount of information.

Therefore, to open a wide path to modern knowledge, to improve the teaching effective use of new information technologies has become a requirement of today.

However, significant changes are taking place in the education system. Educational institutions in the educational system the use of sites created for training is being used.

Another advantage of sites created for educational institutions is that the student he can study at his convenience and even without leaving work.

Another advantage of sites created for educational institutions is to study on them

The term is determined by the student himself, that is, the student begins to study the materials at the time of his choice learns under the supervision of the teacher. Depending on the completion of mastering assignments, tests is determined. The faster the student learns the given program, the faster he can study completes and receives a certificate. If you can't master the program, work on it independently and continue studying will be given the opportunity to continue.

Mainly the given materials on sites created for educational institutions will consist of:

- Textbook;
- Audio and video textbooks;
- Online lessons (web page);
- Electronic libraries;
- Tests;
- Multimedia - electronic textbooks [13].

Our republic was created for educational institutions in higher and secondary specialized educational institutions cataloging of sites, e-learning prepared in republican educational institutions promoting literature among all educational institutions is an important and complex task is considered Finding a positive solution to this issue by the leadership of our country e-learning resources created for educational institutions and sites of educational institutions serious attention is paid to the implementation of the educational process. As a result of this, Uzbekistan the information and education portal <http://www.ziyonet.uz/> established by the decision of the President of the Republic has been launched and educational resources for all educational institutions are available on this portal placement is important.

Traditional and electronic educational materials are part of a unified educational environment complementing each other is considered important. New information technologies the use of opportunities serves to eliminate some pedagogical problems.

The goal is that the creation of a single information portal will lead to the following positive results made by:

- A unified information environment of republican pedagogic educational institutions will be created;
 - creates a unified library environment (creation of an electronic library, electronic formation of a fund of textbooks and non-traditional information carriers, uniform information creation of the base and so on.);
 - a unified telecommunication network environment is formed in the field of pedagogical education;
 - forms a new information-educational environment, information and communication in education creates the socio-psychological foundations of using technologies;
 - pedagogy by forming pedagogical personnel with a new information culture increases the quality of education;
 - creates a system of scientific and methodological support of new educational technologies;
 - providing public access to educational information, information resources, documents transmission, systematization of the accounting mechanism, the state of pedagogical education in the republic information on the public will be made available;
 - distance education system will be developed.

The introduction of a single information space of pedagogic educational institutions is pedagogic creates good conditions for the development of the quality of education and information supply.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, it can be concluded that activity in educational institutions leading professors and teachers, especially informatics teachers, and the educational institution among the

students, students who are interested together, the site of this educational institution they are important participants in creating and updating the content. In view of these including innovative teaching methods and interactive ideas in the higher education process on the basis of scientifically based opinions on increasing the effectiveness of educational processes considered.

The analysis of these scientific research shows that information in the higher education system the use of communication technologies has its positive and negative aspects. Advantages: saving time and money; development of distance education technologies; improving the preparation of e-books and courses by teachers; the risk of getting sick reduce; is to create equal opportunities for students to learn. Disadvantages: individual performance difficulties; complexity of knowledge assessment; scientific research decrease in activity; technological inequality among students; directly with students lack of communication.

Experiments show that modern science and technology development is the teacher's to be creative, to teach one's subject based on an innovative approach, interactive method and effective use of tools, ability to think freely about important problems of science, to be able to convey the achievements of science to students and, finally, students to creative thinking, research requires that he be able to teach his work. Therefore, the teacher is primarily an information technology it is necessary to acquire the qualifications.

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